

UPSTREAM ATTENUATION OF INTAKE DISTORTION DUE TO ENGINE-INTAKE INTERACTION - A NUMERICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Intake distortion remains a critical factor affecting compressor performance, stability, and structural integrity in jet engines. Low-fidelity models, such as the parallel compressor model, often fail to capture upstream attenuation, which is defined as the compressor's aerodynamic response to distorted inflow. This study presents numerical investigations of a generic circumferential stagnation pressure distortion, confirming attenuation effects in CFD studies and identifying two distinct contributing phenomena: compressor-distortion interaction and flowpath contraction, the latter being dominant. Attenuation levels of up to 63 per-cent between the Aerodynamic Interface Plane (AIP) and Rotor Entry Plane (REP) inform the need to incorporate both effects into next generation parallel compressor models. When employing high fidelity CFD, reducing numerical boundary condition influence is crucial. Boundary condition (BC) related reflections were mitigated using spectral non-reflecting BCs (NRBCs) and filtered Riemann BCs. Comparative analysis of Harmonic Balance (HB) and Unsteady RANS (URANS) methods showed consistent results, with remaining discrepancies likely due to boundary condition influences. Euler-based flux vector-splitting methods captured basic attenuation, but currently fall short of predicting the full scale of effects. Refinement through quasi-3D implementations could bridge that gap. Additionally, RANS simulations of empty ducts revealed highly similar distortion progression as URANS and HB methods that included a compressor.

Keywords: Upstream Attenuation, Intake, Inlet, Distortion, Harmonic Balance, URANS, Euler

NOMENCLATURE

AIP	Aerodynamic Interface Plane
BC	Boundary Condition
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
DC	Distortion Coefficient
DI	Distortion Intensity
LF	Load Factor
NRBC	Non-Reflective Boundary Condition
p	Static Pressure [Pa]
p_t	Stagnation Pressure [Pa]
REP	Rotor Entry Plane
Θ	Circumferential Coordinate [°]

1 INTRODUCTION

In both civil and military applications, various aspects of aircraft design and operation can cause distorted inflow to the jet engine and thus also the compressor. This, in turn, affects performance, aerodynamic stability and in some cases even structural integrity of the engine. The compressor's answer can be derived by e.g. parallel compressor models [1], which employ the undistorted compressor characteristics for evaluation of any changes in operating points. More advanced models rely on stage or even row characteristics [2]. Enhancements in the design process over the past decades have already reduced the reserve of surge margin. Improving the low-fidelity models used to determine the reserve attributed to intake distortion is thus a crucial step on the way to engines with lower fuel consumption and higher distortion tolerance.

One potential weakness of current generation parallel com-

pressor models lies in the position where that measurement data for evaluating intake distortion is collected. *Intake Distortion* is frequently measured in the *Aerodynamic Interface Plane* (AIP) [3], some distance from the first blade row. This leaves a potentially critical gap if AIP and Rotor Entry Plane (REP) are some distance apart, as the distortion is apt to change in intensity and form, especially for longer gaps between those two planes.

Upstream attenuation is the result of the - often unsteady - interaction of a compressor and intake distortion. A primary example would be a static pressure deficit as the compressor's upstream answer to a stagnation pressure distortion. Upstream Attenuation has previously been reported on, especially in experimental setups comparing far-coupling and close-coupling a compressor and its intake duct [4]. The affected domain is documented to span 1 to up to 3.34 radii upstream of the rotor intake plane.

Under the influence of intake distortion, the compressor has been observed to redistribute mass flow and induce swirl upstream. This resulted in a reduction of mass flow asymmetries originating from the intake distortion, resulting in areas of lower static pressure matching the position of the stagnation pressure deficit. With progression in direction of the compressor entry, distorted areas have been reported to lessen in intensity up until the REP [5]. At the same time, the stagnation point at the spinner tip drifts towards the undistorted area.

Early attempts at predicting attenuation of intake distortion, in form of static pressure and velocity redistribution, can be dated to the early 1970ies by Callahan and Stenning [6]. They proposed conducting a small perturbations analysis of inviscid, compressible flow in a first order formulation. Perturbation speed components are used to predict deviations in static pressure compared to undistorted compressor operation. The method uses the normalised slope of the static pressure rise over axial velocity at constant speed for predictions of compressor stability and upstream effects. Callahan and Stenning predict different levels of attenuation depending on the relative radial position of a streamtube, with the attenuation at the compressor tip reaching higher levels. This difference is attributed to radial cross flows, which would typically be present in an engine, but are not represented by this midstream formulation. Another major influence is found in the Mach number, with low subsonic Mach numbers changing the amount of attenuation, and higher Mach numbers changing the inception point of attenuation. Their work accounts for high subsonic Mach numbers of up to 0.8, depending on the compressor architecture.

In response, Greitzer [7] raised concerns as to the lack of differentiation between compressors with and without inlet guide vanes, as this difference might lead to different attenuating influences. Also, inconsistencies for higher Mach numbers (still in high subsonic areas) have been criticised. The alternative model is of higher sophistication, as it relies on actuator disks. The implementation is assumed to be not only inviscid, but also in-

compressible, and thus also relies on drastic simplifications. The assumption of constant rotor outflow angles has been proven incorrect by many experimental and numerical studies with higher order models.

Both Callahan and Stenning [6], as well as Greitzer [7], attribute certain modeling discrepancies to unsteady rotor effects. These effects are typically neglected by low-fidelity models, which also offer limited resolution and are currently outdated. Modern unsteady RANS methods are in theory able to capture this unsteady part of upstream attenuation by incorporating viscous effects and higher-order spatial discretisation. These improvements promise to deepen the understanding of upstream attenuation beyond the scope of previous studies known to the authors. This is of particular interest for highly transonic compressors. As of yet no overview of the eligibility of modelling approaches exists. On top of that, drawing upon knowledge gained from higher order CFD simulations to enhance lower order models would be a crucial success in lowering computation times in the design process.

2 METHODOLOGY

The study vehicle is the front stage (rotor and stator) of the three booster stages of the compressor of the MexJET research engine [8] to conserve computational power. The first stage of MexJET (cf. fig 1) is highly transonic at high part-speed, which is modelled in this study. This transonic behaviour justifies concentrating the studies on the first stage, the upstream effects of downstream stages are expected to be of much smaller order than the potential flow field exuded by the rotor shock system.

The duct in front of the rotor extends to a length of 4 casing radii upstream of the REP. This length has been chosen to surpass both the domain with known upstream influence (as visible in the results from [8]) as well as previous observations by Rademaakers [4] of upstream influence of up to 3.4 radii, at the example of a Larzac04 engine. As Larzac04 and MexJET both have a transonic rotor as the first stage, similarity was deemed high enough to use it as a reference for largest possible domains of influence.

Furthermore, a meshing study was performed to ascertain mesh independence, but is not shown here for reasons of brevity. The criteria for that study include adequate representation of compressor operation itself, but also the propagation of shock information in the intake duct, which depends on axial mesh refinement.

Comparisons are derived from a second reference case, a bladeless duct with the same flowpath as MexJET. These calculations were performed on a mesh that was kept highly similar in axial and radial distribution, as well as similar in circumferential refinement from freestream areas of the MexJET. Therefore, conclusions drawn in regard to axial decay and circumferential mixing are comparable between both study vehicles. Further compa-

FIGURE 1: Schematic MexJET Compressor Stage with Calculation Domain and Analysis Surfaces

reliability was received by conserving constant mass flow between each undistorted case at constant intake conditions.

2.1 Numerical Methods

The majority of the studies discussed throughout this work has been conducted in TRACE, a solver developed conjointly by MTU Aero Engines AG and the DLR [9]. When using TRACE within this study, unsteady methods have been employed whenever the compressor was included, due to the unsteady nature of the aforementioned unsteady rotor effects. RANS was used for initialisation purposes of undistorted cases and for the empty duct. For the duct with a compressor, time-domain URANS calculations with dual timestepping have been performed for both distorted and undistorted cases. Additionally, frequency-domain calculations with a harmonic balance (HB) approach [10] have been tested for both usability and reliability. In the HB setup, both the rotor modes and the eigenmodes of the distortion have been respectively prescribed via a high single-digit number of harmonics, whereas the stator influence was reduced to a time-average. In the following, URANS will be used as an abbreviation for all time-domain computations and HB for all frequency-domain ones. In all cases of TRACE usage, the turbulence is modelled according to the Wilcox- $k-\omega$ model.

An instationary, first order spatial Euler-based solver is considered and evaluated for the reliability of predicting upstream attenuation as well. The code used in this study is based on vector-flux splitting found in the works of Vinckier [11]. The flux-splitting solves Euler equations with an error in the magnitude of the truncation error, and is highly robust across shocks in trans- and supersonic flow. The formulation via flux-splitting has been proven in 1D models to conserve total enthalpy and mass flow across shocks. This is accomplished by iterating the weights of the shock location within a grid cell starting from a central difference scheme.

The solver has previously been employed in prediction of blade forces under surge load by Schoenenborn and Breuer [12] and follows the two-dimensional implementation according to

Vinckier [13]. It discretises the compressor and its surrounding domain in axial and circumferential direction, and thus reduces the simulation to a mean-line approach. This in turn enables rapid calculations with computational efforts covered by personal workstations.

Employing such a low effort and low fidelity method is based on the following a-priori considerations of the nature of compressor-intake interaction. The area upstream of the compressor entry plane is influenced very little by phenomena based on losses and friction, when comparing the amount of fluid in boundary layers against the volume of the free flow. Therefore, an Euler-based formulation is expected to capture the dominant large-scale components of the phenomenon.

2.2 Distorted Intake Condition

The aim of this study is manifold: firstly, to prove that upstream attenuation is reproduced by numerical methods. Secondly, it aims to attribute aspects of upstream attenuation to certain flow features. The third purpose of this study is to compare different unsteady calculation methods with respect to their prognosis. Therefore, the compressor is subjected to generic, albeit plausible distortion levels. This study focusses on purely circumferential distortion - both to ease the analysis as well as study the distortion type that is deemed more influential to compressor stability compared to radial distortion [3]. The stagnation pressure distribution measured at the AIP in previous experiments detailed by Kaechele [8], is analysed for the most significant circumferential distortion, corresponding to approximately a 15 per-cent loss in stagnation pressure. This reduced subset is subsequently fitted using a Gaussian function (cf. fig. 2).

FIGURE 2: Gauss Fitting of distorted stagnation pressure

Further aim is to prescribe the intake distortion in a manner that is most conducive to not forcing an implicit compressor answer by any peculiarities attributed to boundary conditions. For time-domain URANS, a modal gust boundary condition, formulated for primitive variables is prescribed to a full-annulus cal-

TABLE 1: Overview of the five cases compared in this study.

Case	Compressor	Numerical Method	Intake Distortion	Intake Boundary Condition
Reference 1: Undistorted Compressor	✓	URANS	✗	0D Riemann
Reference 2: Decay in an empty Duct	✗	RANS	✓	2D Riemann
Case 1: Unsteady RANS	✓	URANS	✓	NRBC
Case 2: Harmonic Balance	✓	HB	✓	2D Riemann with Disk
Case 3: Euler Method	✓	Euler	✓	1D Riemann

ulation based on a circumferential FFT of the distortion pattern. This fulfils the concept of a spectral non-reflective boundary condition (NRBC) according to [14] to minimise reflection.

To conserve computational power, the harmonic balance approach is chosen, which only requires to simulate a single passage. This is paired with a two-dimensional Riemann boundary condition in front of a slim disk with inviscid walls. The interface in between disk and single-passage-domain is configured to transport only the time-averaged zeroth harmonic, and thus minimises interaction between the upstream compressor influence and the numerical reflectiveness of the Riemann BC.

RANS simulations of an empty duct are also conducted with 2D Riemann BCs as no upstream attenuation exists. The Euler method employed is intrinsically relying on Riemann formulation of the intake boundary condition.

2.3 Distortion Parameters

In accordance with SAE-Standards [3], the circumferential severity of any intake distortion can be calculated as the distortion coefficient over a 60 degree segment:

$$DC_{60} = \frac{\overline{P_t} - \overline{P_{t,min,60^\circ}}}{\overline{q_{AIP}}} \quad (1)$$

The authors are well-aware of the discussion surrounding the reliability of the DC_{60} , as several different distortion patterns can be described by the same value. Nonetheless, the distortion coefficient is well-known in literature and thus provides established means of comparison on an academic level. The generic formulation leaves out a coupling to the critical sector of this very compressor, and thus any surge margin predictions, which are not the focus of this study. As said focus pertains to flow changes in front of the compressor, additional characterisations of distortion levels are investigated as well to close this gap.

The distortion intensity is defined as

$$DI = \frac{P_{t,min}}{P_{t,undist.}} \quad (2)$$

to capture effects in variation of the stagnation pressure deficit magnitude.

Additionally, the aerodynamical load generated by wall pressure on the perimeter of the duct wall in a plane with $x = const$ as defined in [15] is evaluated.

$$L = \oint_P p_{wall}(\theta) d\theta \quad (3)$$

For comparability, the load of one analysis surface i in a distorted case is de-dimensioned with the load of the undistorted reference case in the same position to receive the Load Factor LF .

$$LF_i = \frac{L_{dist,i}}{L_{undist,i}} \quad (4)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the preliminary stage, re-analysis of the measurement data from [8] revealed that the compressor displayed upstream effects up to at least 2.4 radii upstream of the rotor entry plane by means of static pressure variance and induced swirl. In simulation of undistorted comparison cases, upstream potential field effects exceeded 2 radii upstream as well. This confirmed the chosen duct length to be a constructive choice.

3.1 Reference 1: Undistorted Compressor

The reference case in figs. 3 and 4 is calculated for an undistorted compressor with a duct stretching to -4 casing radii upstream of the REP via URANS. Each distorted case's nondimensionalised values have been calculated from undistorted references produced with the matching geometry and numerical method. To avoid repetition, only one representative, undistorted case is discussed here. The undistorted reference cases have been generated to become independent from slightly different predictions of shock positions originating in the highly transonic rotor tip region to avoid purely numerical influencing the attenuation measures.

FIGURE 3: Axial development of stagnation pressure in undistorted URANS calculations

Both static and stagnation pressure levels in figures 3 and 4 display perfect periodicity, which matches the prescribed periodic compressor build. The flowpath of the compressor starts to contract at slightly less than $-0.5R$ upstream of the rotor entry.

Stagnation pressure in fig. 3 is properly homogeneous in large distances from the compressor. In the chosen scales, first upstream influence is visible in form of periodic spikes 2 radii in front of the REP. These start in the tip region, which is informed by the upstream propagation of the rotor shock system. Connection of these spikes to shock influence areas has been verified without display in this paper. Areas of lower stagnation pressure grow from tip to hub with greater nearness to the REP, with the tip region showing the greatest variation in stagnation pressure levels. These spikes are of constant circumferential coordinate per spike up unto $-0.125R$ before the REP. From this plane onward, the pattern is twisted co-rotationally, indicating an influence area of swirl. In the REP itself, the stagnation pressure variation spans the complete radial expanse from hub to tip and

FIGURE 4: Axial development of static pressure in undistorted URANS calculations

amounts to 45 per-cent variation.

The static pressure (cf. fig. 4) shows very similar developments as the stagnation pressure. A distinction can be seen in the hub area, in which stagnation point and boundary layer effects lead to a higher static pressure region. This is also influenced by the flowpath curvature which is more pronounced in the hub than the tip region. Flowpath contraction as a whole lowers static pressure levels according to the convergent nozzle theory with axial progression towards the compressor. The high variation on static pressure reaches differences of up to 63 per-cent near the tip, whereas the values in the hub region are much more homogeneous, even directly in the REP.

Both stagnation pressure as well as static pressure indicate influence of the rotor bow shock up to $-2R$ upstream in the stagnation pressure (cf. fig. 3) and up to $-1R$ in the static pressure (cf. fig. 4) within the chosen scales. These are kept the same for future evaluations within the same simulation method.

FIGURE 5: Axial development of stagnation pressure in an empty Duct

FIGURE 6: Axial development of static pressure in an empty Duct

3.2 Reference 2: Decay in an empty Duct

Another comparison case is derived from an empty duct with a bladeless annulus of the same dimensions as the compressor itself. Total pressure distortion was kept the same, and the outlet static pressure was adapted to gain the same mass flow as in the undistorted case with compressor blades. Therefore, static pressure levels may diverge from those within the compressor, as an empty duct needs a lower static exit pressure to provide enough suction to amount to the same mass flow. Nonetheless, general trends can be analysed.

Starting with the evaluation of the stagnation pressure (cf. fig. 5), the distortion is well-pronounced in the AIP at $-4R$. Within quick succession throughout the axial analysis positions, the pressure loss area shrinks in extent, and the overall pressure loss declines. That decline happens faster at lower radii near the hub. Thus, the distortion develops from a purely circumferential distortion into an impressive combined distortion with radial content. At the REP, the variation between highest and lowest

stagnation pressure amounts to 16 per-cent.

The very first cell layer at $-4R$ contained intense reflective artifacts that are caused by using a Riemann boundary condition. Therefore, for this and any future investigations, a secondary analysis plane few cells downstream from the AIP was introduced and is displayed here. Within these few axial cells, the artifacts reduce significantly, and vanish completely in the next analysis surface at $-3R$. This serves to stress the importance of choosing boundary conditions that reflect intake distortion as little as possible, if any analysis is conducted near the AIP.

The static pressure in fig. 6 shows minor remnants of numeric artifacts in the alternative analysis surface near $-4R$. Up unto $-2R$, no changes in static pressure are reported. Upstream influence of the hub tip stagnation area is already visible nearly half a diameter in front of the spinner cone. This may stem from lower non-axial velocity components that typically enhance mixing out of such phenomena. From fig. 5 (f) onward, an asymmetry of higher static pressure regions on the opposite side than

FIGURE 7: Axial development of stagnation pressure in distorted URANS simulations

FIGURE 8: Axial development of static pressure in distorted URANS simulations

the intake distortion can be made out. This continues even into the plane where the REP would reside, as static pressure levels lower to adhere to mass flow requirements. This drift of the stagnation area to the opposite side of the intake distortion has previously been reported on by Fidalgo [5]. Static pressure variation is much lower with a value of 3 per-cent than in the presence of a compressor stage, so any variation in static pressure is mostly attributed to compressor operation.

3.3 Case 1: Distorted Compressor, Unsteady RANS

URANS clearly shows an influence of the prescribed intake distortion in both stagnation pressure and static pressure, even though the formulation pertained to stagnation pressure only. For URANS, the distortion was formulated as an NRBC in the form of a primitive gust boundary condition. This leads to a slightly lower average stagnation pressure than that of the prescribed BC, the deviation is less than 0.5 per-cent. The formulation via spectral NRBC contains a higher degree of numerical freedom in or-

der to reduce reflection, compared to Riemann. This results in significantly less artifacts than in the previous case. Just as in that empty duct case, the stagnation pressure distortion (cf. fig. 7) shows up in a purely circumferential manner, tapering out circumferentially. Spikes in stagnation pressure near the casing appear similarly to the undistorted compressor case, alas smaller than in the same axial plane at -2R than without the presence of an intake distortion.

Similarly to the progression witnessed in an empty annulus, the area of lower stagnation pressure feathers out when progressing in direction of axial flow. The distortion first gets attenuated in the hub region, potentially by contraction of the flowpath. In addition to the distortion progression in an empty Duct and in contrast to the undistorted compressor, spikes in stagnation pressure near the tip stemming from the tip bow shock cover less radial height at comparable axial position (compare figs. 3 (g) and 7 (g)). Nonetheless, the distortion stays visible up unto the REP, leading to lower pressure variation in the hub region and higher

FIGURE 9: Axial development of stagnation pressure in distorted HB simulations

variation of up to 50 per-cent near the tip. When compared to the attenuation levels of an undistorted compressor (46 per-cent) and an empty duct (16 per-cent), the mismatch resulting from linear superposition of these two cases suggests that attenuation due to the two mechanisms of flowpath contraction and compressor operation behaves in a non-linear way. At the same time, the area of lower stagnation pressure levels is twisted, near the hub in co-rotational direction, but around the casing counter-rotationally. This conforms to the twist in stagnation pressure peaks in front of the blade itself, speaking to different upstream influence mechanisms in area with shock influence and those without.

In terms of static pressure (cf. fig. 8), the compressor answer appears up unto the same distance as the reference case, namely one rotor diameter upstream. The static pressure distribution shows non-periodicity that cannot directly be traced back to the position of the intake distortion itself. Areas of variation larger than in the reference case are introduced in the region between 300 and 360 degrees, while several regions with signifi-

FIGURE 10: Axial development of static pressure in distorted HB simulations

cantly lower variation in static pressure are introduced, e.g. between 60 and 120 deg and 200 to 300 degrees, with an overall slightly higher static pressure. From a quarter rotor diameter onward, the static pressure develops a distortion pattern that mirrors the stagnation pressure pattern (cf. fig. 7 (g)) in the same analysis plane. This can also be characterised as less developed in the hub region and more egregious near the tip. Static pressure variation in the REP amounts to 62 per-cent, undercutting previous values of 63 per-cent without distortion, which is not a significant difference. Compared to the low levels of static pressure variation in an empty duct, this effect is driven purely by the presence of the compressor.

3.4 Case 2: Distorted Compressor, Harmonic Balance

The first remark is that HB and URANS show different stagnation and static pressure levels, even though the prescription of distortion is held as similar as possible. To concentrate on more

significant phenomena attributable to distortion attenuation, figs. 9 and 10 are normalised to the same pressure levels as the distorted URANS case. This normalisation is not applied during the model comparison of section 3.6. Transferring the intake distortion from 2D Riemann to a non-reflective, spectral formulation of a 2D Inlet BC (primitive gust) has been performed whilst keeping stagnation and static pressure levels constant to determine the velocity components necessary for the prescription of primitive gust in the URANS calculations. Minor levels of inaccuracy may have been introduced from averaging the pressure levels used for that calculation, stemming from a priori RANS simulations, which are also used as initialisations. The averaging of 2D pressure might not have preserved the intricacies of 3D velocity components, but this only indicates the difficulties in prescribing total pressure distortion in a non-reflective way.

A reason for different pressure levels after the normalisation at $-4R$ might be the disk approach used in HB calculations to translate a spatially two-dimensional distortion into a spatial and temporal distortion as necessitated by the harmonic balance method. Inside the disk, drift may have led to dissipation as evident in a stagnation pressure level lower than that of the empty duct and raised the respective static pressure level to account for lower velocity incurred in the disk.

Other than minor differences in boundary condition prescription, the HB results show very similar progressions of both stagnation pressure and static pressure along the duct. Inhomogeneities in domain of the rotor tip bow shock influence appear of larger order than in the URANS case. Also, in the plane of $-0.5R$, the radial influence of the bow shock area spans a greater domain, which is reversed in the plane at $-0.25R$. Both of these effects are visible in stagnation as well as static pressure.

In addition to the URANS setup of analysis planes, one more plane has been placed at $-1.25R$, which still telegraphs an influence of the rotor shocks. This additional plane shows that the progression is not subject to abrupt changes in front of the spinner tip. Just as before, the spinner tip stagnation area is expressed by an area of higher static pressure, which in HB is both larger and higher than in URANS.

HB shows the largest variation in static and stagnation pressure levels in the rotor entry plane of 64 per-cent in static and 61 per-cent in stagnation pressure. Incidentally, the maximum pressure levels are also the highest of all cases reviewed here. The minimum pressure levels - be they static or stagnant - are not particularly exceptional in comparison to other minima. As all computations start from the nearly the same stagnation pressure levels in the prescribed intake distortion, this implies that HB exaggerates or URANS underrates discrepancies in static and stagnation pressure levels under intake distortion. Unfortunately, measurement campaigns to assess this discrepancy would need a resolution that is not economically viable. In compressor design from an aerodynamic standpoint, time-averaged pressure levels under intake distortion typically satisfy design requirements. An

FIGURE 11: Axial development of stagnation pressure in distorted Euler simulations

FIGURE 12: Axial development of static pressure in distorted Euler simulations

aeroacoustics’ or aeroelastic engineer may object here drastically.

Further testing of the setup in HB pertaining to which modes to resolve should be conducted to identify the origins of this phenomenon. On top of that, a greater variety of intake boundary conditions should be tested at the same time.

3.5 Case 3: Distorted Compressor, Euler Method

In case of the used Euler model, the first and foremost question is whether the upstream attenuation can be modelled by this low fidelity approach. The ability of Euler methods to compute upstream attenuation in form of static and stagnation pressure adaption throughout the intake leading up to the REP is affirmed in figs. 11 and 12.

Detailed analysis of stagnation pressure levels in fig 11 a) indicates that the severity of the distortion lessens by nearly 3 percentage points from the AIP unto the start of the nose cone. Further dissipation is not predicted in the area of the flowpath contracting by influence of the nose cone unto the REP. The Euler model also does not provide information about the interaction with singular blades such as in the case of previous modelling approaches. Neither does the formulation at half radial span include any special features of hub- or tip-near regions.

The Euler model also predicts an intense compressor answer to intake distortion in form of static pressure inhomogeneity, which is not on par with other models' predictions. The patterns experienced in this quantity can also be divided up into the area of a constant, axial flow path as well as the contraction along the axial extent of the nose cone. In front of the nose cone (cf. fig. 12 a)) the static pressure experiences a reduction whilst nearing the REP, up until 7 per-cent lower than in the undistorted region in the same plane. Both stagnation as well as static pressure see a slight offset of the pressure minimum position from the prescription which was precisely placed at 180 degrees. That offset is in the order of mesh resolution of this particular implementation, and thus inconclusive.

Of greater reliability is the changed pattern in the domain of the nose cone, where static pressure (cf. fig. 12 b)) exhibits a strong asymmetry in combination of lower static pressure levels in the vicinity of the REP. Whilst overall pressure levels decline by 5 per-cent, the variation amounts to 3 percentage points at maximum pressure, surpassing the average. The undercutting is of lower impact at 2 percentage points. Surpassing the average happens in the mathematically positive sense of rotation, which is also corotational to the compressor rotation. Thus, a heightened static pressure region is caused by the advance of the potential field of the transonic rotor, followed by a lower static pressure region attributed to the dissipation of energy across the rotor shock. This asymmetry is highest right in front of the rotor, and is dissipated in circumferential direction with longer axial distance to the rotor leading edge.

Another insight may be gained in the future by comparing ensemble averages of URANS or HB with Euler model results. As it is, Euler predicts a variation of stagnation pressure in the same order of magnitude as in the empty duct as it does not resolve individual blade response. This in turn suggests that the diminishing of the stagnation pressure is not caused by friction in wall boundary layers.

3.6 Model Comparison

To quantitatively compare different simulation approaches, derived variables per plane such as DC60, Load Factor and distortion intensity DI are evaluated. It is therewithin important to consider which flow property is represented by each of these formulations. The DC60 will heavily depend on dynamic pressure in the AIP and the form of the distortion itself. The distortion form in this study is easy to digest for any numerical methods through its continuous slopes, but the DC60 is lower than for a distortion with a fuller profile at the same distortion intensity. Said distortion intensity represents the maximum variation in stagnation pressure between distorted and undistorted areas. A Load Factor of 1 implies that the static wall pressure distribution in the undistorted and distorted cases lead to the same aerodynamic load within the circumference of one plane. In compari-

FIGURE 13: DC60 over axial distance

FIGURE 14: Distortion Intensity over axial distance

son to DC60 and DI which are derived from radial averages, the Load Factor encompasses the direct values at the wall.

The DC60 in fig. 13 shows very similar trends in all distorted cases. Namely, that a first region from $-4R$ in the AIP to $-0.5R$, near the spinner contracting the flowpath, shows one distinct slope. All simulations performed by TRACE show the same inception point of change in slope of DC60 progression at $-0.5R$, whereas the Euler model predicts an earlier influence of the spinner in the region of $-1.25R$ to $-1R$. Refining the analysis resolution in the future can reveal whether the inception point is actually predicted with such large of a disparity or whether the coarse axial refinement used for analysis purposes is to fault.

Whereas URANS and HB display very similar predictions of lowering DC60 by respectively 0.5 and 0.51 points, the empty duct leads to a more significant lowering of 0.66 points. In comparison to that, the Euler Model only predicts an attenuation of 0.36 points unto the REP. For Euler, the difference in stagnation pressure between face average and distorted sector aver-

FIGURE 15: Nondimensional Load Factor respective to load in undistorted reference cases in same axial position over axial distance

age far exceeds the dynamic pressure in the AIP. This is due to the fact that Euler underpredicts average static pressure levels less severely than average stagnation pressure levels at $-4R$. This leads to an inflation of the dynamic pressure.

One qualitative difference between compressor and empty annulus is the additional curvature before the nose cone starts, most prominent in between $-2R$ and $-1R$. This indicates that the empty annulus potentially reaches even lower levels of DC60 without the presence of the spinner, but that this is corrected by the upstream effect of the back pressure originating at the spinner tip.

Distortion intensity (cf. fig. 14) shows falling trends with greater proximity to the REP, mostly without or only with little kinks. Distortion attenuation nearly halts as soon as the spinner contracts the flowpath. The Euler model suffers from the already mentioned high overall stagnation pressure level, and thus does not alleviate DI beyond 3.1 percentage points. This is surpassed by all TRACE calculations, as these predict an attenuation of 5 to 6 percentage points. The empty duct results in the lowest level of DI at REP with less than 6 per-cent remaining, whereas HB shows the lowest attenuation. As the same time, the boundary condition used in conjunction with HB also already lessens the severity of the stagnation pressure distortion. This has to be kept in mind when employing this combination, and potentially needs to be mitigated iteratively.

From an aerodynamic perspective, this indicates that the compressor conserves some amount of the width of the streamtube that contains the highest stagnation pressure deficit by suctioning force. Lacking a compressor, this streamtube is apt to widen more thus and lessen the severity of stagnation pressure deficit above that encountered with a compressor. This would indicate that there is an upstream effect of the compressor on the

flow in form of interacting with the distortion itself. But when correcting for flowpath contraction, the compressor has the opposite effect on stagnation pressure than what has previously been described in literature (compare [5], [6]). This hypothesis will have to be confirmed further in the future and may not hold up for subsonic operating points.

The Load Factor at first appears in a disjointed manner, as each case sits on a different absolute level. Nonetheless, in all cases, the quotient of static wall pressure integral between distorted and undistorted analysis planes rises continuously and by a similar range of 2.5 per-cent. The overall different levels can be attributed to the fact that each model predicts different static pressure levels, a circumstance that should be substantiated experimentally.

Calculation times are a major factor in all design processes, but the impact is even higher for purposes of evaluating intake distortion. This originates from the need to simulate full annulus geometries when researching influence of circumferential of combined intake distortion. The TRACE calculations of the empty duct and any compressor cases used the same number of cores, in relation to mesh cells. Highest was the time expense of the URANS calculations with high single-digit numbers of weeks. In comparison, the HB calculations took around a week, but required more finessing of the setup. The empty duct was calculated as RANS and thus reached convergence within mere hours. All of this was undercut steeply by the Euler model that ran for less than an hour, single core, on a user's workstation.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

A generic, circumferential stagnation pressure distortion has been prepared. The need to minimise reflection of boundary conditions in the context of this study has been identified, confirmed and treated by testing several boundary condition prescription methods. The most promising ones are employing a robust implementation of spectral NRBCs and buffering the impact of reflection of Riemann BC by filtering the reflection through a disk in front of the actual domain of interest.

First and foremost, upstream attenuation, as previously defined in literature, has been shown in numerical studies. Secondly, upstream attenuation has been identified to consist of at least two separate phenomena. A compressor interaction with the intake distortion has been shown through comparison of an empty duct and a distorted compressor in the opposite way as previously described in literature. On top of that, the influence of flowpath contraction has been proven to surpass and ameliorate the interactive influence. Upstream attenuation as a whole is of large and relevant dimension, as the distortion level from the AIP up to rotor entry suffered attenuation of up to 63 per-cent DC60. Therefore, both effects should be integrated into next generation parallel compressor models after studying them under a wider range of influences. These influences are speculated to

originate in compressor architecture, distortion form, operating and throttling point.

Thirdly, HB and URANS have proven to deliver results of very similar quality. Remaining quantitative differences in levels of stagnation and static pressure most likely majorly stem from boundary condition effects. The eligibility of URANS and HB needs to be evaluated further by experimental data, to remove uncertainties pertaining to the pressure levels. Any experimental setup produced for this purpose would also greatly benefit from capturing the progression of distortion through an empty duct. Fourthly, alternative calculation methods have been tested. At the current status of euler flux vector-splitting models, meanline implementations are to be treated with caution. Nonetheless, they provide an indication of attenuation trends and should be reevaluated after implementation of a quasi-3D approach that adheres to the radial pressure equilibrium. Meanwhile, RANS calculations of empty ducts with the matching compressor annulus without blades has provided good insights into the progression of intake distortion. It was able to capture the transformation from a purely circumferential into a combined distortion with radial variation.

The amount of attenuation and redistribution of intake distortion underlines the importance to include these effects in next generation Parallel Compressor Models. Improved Euler models that build upon the data generated during this study would make a welcome addition.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Calculations for the empty duct and Euler cases performed by AH, supervision of RF by AH, conceptualisation, correspondence and textualisation by AH. URANS and HB calculations performed by RF, resulting in figures 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10 and partial data for several more. Academical supervision and proof-reading attributed to DK.

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